

THE EFFECTS OF POOR READING AND WRITING IN THE ATTAINMENT OF QUALITY EDUCATION IN TSHWANE WEST DISTRICT PRIMARY SCHOOLS IN PRETORIA

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ABSTRACT

This qualitative study aimed to ascertain the effects of poor reading and writing on the attainment of quality education in primary schools in the Tshwane West District. A sample of four Heads of Departments and eight teachers were purposively and non-randomly selected to take part in the study. The face-to-face interviews were conducted using Tikly's model for understanding education quality in Africa. This assisted in the framing of the interview questions and bringing relevance to the needs of the study. The study found that issues relating to language barriers, lack of parental involvement, overcrowding, and resources are the main causes that affect the attainment of quality education in primary schools around the Tshwane West district, are rife. This then showed that the policy from the Department of Education does not coerce the community to work hand in hand with the school to jointly assist the learners in reading and writing. The recommendation is that there should be a policy change that should ensure that there is synergy between the community and the schools to assist learners with reading and writing that would address issues of a language barrier, overcrowding, and resources.

Keywords: Quality education, reading, writing, parental involvement

INTRODUCTION

Garira (2020) states that Quality Education (QE) in schools requires an accurate description of all its components to judge its realization and plan for its improvement and facilitate an understanding of the quality of education. To add to that, Dwi, and Fook (2022) say that Indonesian schools resorted to focusing on student learning outcomes to attain QE. This was their priority to the satisfaction of the Indonesian national goals that they have in place. Lewin & Little (2011) indicate that globally there are still 67 million children out of school, 43% of whom live in Africa. Many of these children live in conflict areas or 'fragile' states and many more live in rural areas. Every year ten million children drop out of primary school in Sub Sahara Africa due to various reasons, which range from challenges to reading and writing. This study was triggered by Mokoma's (2018) study that indicates that Tshwane West District school's results, in North of

Pretoria, South Africa, are poor and underperforming because of problems in reading and writing among children in primary schools. This led to the underperforming of schools with the poor pass rate being on the rise, which indicates the seriousness of poor-quality education. The researchers' concern about this investigation is that learners are unable to read and write, and they are underperforming, hence high failure rate persists especially at the primary school level. These unresolved issues may continue to affect the learners' progress toward their high school levels. This would then be contradictory to the Department of Education, (DoE), Admission Policy of 1998 which states that no learner should repeat a grade more than once in a phase. In a nutshell, this could compromise the attainment of QE which could affect the learners' progress to the higher grades because of problems in reading and writing. McBride (2019) says that eight out of every ten children in South Africa cannot read properly: not in English, not in their home language, not in any language. According to the Progress in International Reading Literacy Study (Department of Basic Education, DBE, 2023), an international comparative reading assessment: 78% of Grade 4 learners in South Africa cannot read for meaning, and this is significantly worse for children tested in African languages. This study then aimed to investigate the effects of poor reading and writing on the attainment of QE in the primary schools around Tshwane West District in Pretoria.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The literature review of the study aimed to place the study context against the known international facts on challenges of poor reading and writing. The researchers think that if learners are unable to read and write at the primary school level, even after being taught to do so, then there is a bleak future ahead because one of the main purposes of primary school education is to lay down the foundation of learning through reading and writing. With the primary school learners still being put under the 'radar' by both the teachers and their parents, the study made use of Tikly's 'three legs' of the roles played by the 'Home and community, The School, and the Policy environments' (Tikly, 2011).

Figure 1: A framework for understanding education quality in Africa (Tikly, 2011)

Figure 1 shows that there should be policies that assist in shaping the schooling system to attain QE. These policies should clarify the roles that the home and the community should play in assisting learners with schoolwork; this would ensure that learners become settled in the school environment because there would be support from the home, which is also received in the schooling system. According to Tikly (2011), many African countries face a crisis in teacher morale, which could be a gap in the policy part. The issue of home and community involvement in education cannot be separated from the school issues. This was attested by Tikly (2003 & 2010), who said that the more parents are kept in the loop of what is happening in the schools, the more accountable they become. In countries like Tanzania and India, there are initiatives like Uwezo and Pratham, respectively, which were formed as a way of bringing the community and the school together (Tikly, 2011). The issue of a working policy in the environment (school), could come in handy to assist with the alignment of teaching where issues of resources, infrastructure, and mandatory staff development are enforced (Tikly, 2011). This would ensure that enough books are sought for learners to be capacitated with reading but besides that, teachers would be empowered to go to workshops where reading pedagogies are enhanced in them. Thus, Tikly's framework for understanding the QE assisted the study in understanding the challenges that learners have in reading and writing that impact the QE. The lens through which these challenges were looked at was from the Heads of Departments (HoDs) and teachers who were entrusted with the responsibility of what it is that they experience on the ground since they work with these kids daily. Lucas (2011) and Rany (2013) also note that pupils may have a low reading ability due to school heads not availing the necessary course books for practice reading, lack of appropriate curriculum to help improve pupils' reading abilities, and classroom environments that are crowded and noisy. These could be some of the reasons that the schools where this study was conducted are because of the remote area where they are placed.

METHODOLOGY

Myers (2009) states that the research method is a strategy of inquiry, which moves from the underlying assumptions to research design and data collection. A research design on the other hand is a structure that incorporates all elements of a research project. It is the arrangement of conditions for the collection and analysis of data in a manner that aims to combine relevance to the research purpose (Akhtar, 2016). The study made use of a case study design because the focus was on primary schools in the same district which often enroll kids that some of them come from pre-schools that are the same and even the said primary schools, are of the same quintiles where they are mainly under-resourced and overcrowded. The study was qualitative in nature. Sutton and Austin (2015) state that qualitative research can help researchers access the thoughts and feelings of research participants, which can enable the development of an understanding of the meaning that people ascribe to their experiences, and why such behaviors take place. Therefore, the study was informed by the qualitative approach because the aim was to understand the phenomenon that the HoDs and teachers experience from the type of learners that they have. According to Kivunja and Kuyini (2017), the word paradigm in research means "a philosophical way of thinking or basic set of beliefs that guides research action or an investigation". The study adopted the interpretivism paradigm because it employs methods that generate qualitative data employing an open-ended interview structure (standardized open-ended, semi-standardized open-ended, and informal interviews (Rehman & Alharthi, 2016). The reason for that is that the researchers wanted to get the understating of participants in terms of challenges towards the attainment of quality education. Thematic analysis was used to analyse data where the participants' responses were grouped, and similarities were extracted for consolidation of findings.

POPULATION

Momoh (2021) defines a population as a distinct group of individuals whether that group comprises a nation or a group of people with a common characteristic. The study population was 96 primary schools from the Tshwane West District, North of Pretoria which comprises 151 schools. This constituted 151 principals (which were not part of the study), more than 600 HoDs, and more than 12 000 teachers.

SAMPLING

Sampling is the practice of selecting definite members or a subset of the population to make statistical readings and estimate characteristics of the study population technique based on the theory of probability; the method reflects every member and forms a sample based on a fixed process (Bhattacharjee, 2012). The sample for the study was a probable one and comprised four primary schools with four Heads of Departments (HoDs), and 8 of its teachers (two teachers per school). The researchers adopted non-probability sampling techniques called purposive sampling in this investigation. According to Etikan, et al (2016), purposive sampling is the deliberate choice of a participant due to the qualities the participant possesses. The participants were conveniently selected because they were not supposed to be of a particular discipline or subject, but they were selected because they teach in the primary schools of Tshwane West District. The reason for trimming the schools to four is for the researcher's convenience to access them. Schools were given labels like School A, B, etc., while the HoDs were referred to as HoD1, HoD2, etc., and T1, and T2 was used to refer to the teachers. Data were analysed thematically for all the participants and the questions that they were responding to, were designed from the three legs of Tikly's conceptual framework towards QE. Data were collected through face-to-face interviews with the participants. Each interview was between 15 and 25 minutes.

RESULTS

The study findings assisted the study in ascertaining the impact that poor reading and writing skills have on the attainment of QE in the primary schools of the Tshwane West District in north Pretoria.

HEAD OF DEPARTMENTS' INTERVIEW FINDINGS

When asked what the policy stipulates in assisting the school to attain quality education, the HoDs' responses produced two themes that also cut across what the schools do towards the attainment of quality education. These themes came out as gaps that the policy document is having:

- Lack of clarity on language issues
- Lack of clarity on parental involvement

When responding to the question on the role of policy towards learning, the HoDs said the following under the theme:

LACK OF CLARITY ON LANGUAGE ISSUES

HoD2 said: *"We have a challenge in our school because we do not have a policy that protects us to screen the learners. Our schools have a lot of learners who do not understand the language of conversation that we use at the school and that affects communication"*. To add to that, HoD3 said: *"As you can see, we are based in the middle of informal settlement and we often receive learners whose parents are from our neighbouring countries and as such, we take almost 8 months teaching them how to speak our language"*. The HoDs were also asked to comment on the role of parents in their children's education.

LACK OF CLARITY ON PARENTAL INVOLVEMENT

HoD1 said: *"We believe that the parents do assist willingly but they too are not conversant with our Language of Learning and Teaching (LoLT) and as such, we continue to experience a lot of learners who come to school without having done their homework"*. HoD1 added and said: *"Learners are failing to achieve their basic education because they lack parental support and need to be assisted with homework"* (HoD1). HoD3 said: *"It does not seem like parents do come to the party when it comes to their kids' learning because they are not coerced by any policy, and this is because they too are unable to speak most of the commonly used language of conversations in our schools"*. HoD3 added and said: *"Learners drop out in numbers and parents do not even report that to the school while they see these learners at home and not in schools"*.

TEACHERS' INTERVIEW FINDINGS

The primary school teachers shared similar sentiments to those that their HoDs have given. When asked about their perceived challenges that hamper the attainment of QE, they too centred their responses on issues pertaining to reading and writing, especially in the foundation phase. Their responses produced five themes:

- Lack of resources
- Parental involvement
- Language barrier
- Overcrowding

When the teachers responded on the issues that relate to the existing policies to run the school, the school issues, and those of the home and the community, the above themes emerged, and the responses were as follows:

LACK OF RESOURCES

Teacher 1 (T1) from school A said: *"Our school tries to improvise and come up with some avenues of achieving QE, but we are still running short in that regard because we have a lot of learners, and I am not sure if that does affect the budget to secure textbooks and other stuff. She further said that their school is disadvantaged by a shortage of teaching and learning support materials other than textbooks, study guides, teacher's guides, smartboards, computers, and human resources"*. To add to that T2 said: Teacher 3 (T3) from school C said: *"As teachers, our mandate is to impart knowledge to learners and communities. But we are unable to perform this responsibility to our level best due to the limit of teachers' support materials at school. Our school does not have teaching aids or models, for example, compasses, globe maps, flashcards, test*

tubes, thermometers, etc. That would assist in the easy understanding of learners. The learners learn best when they see and touch things unlike giving them theory knowledge only. Learning is when a child can memorize what was taught, and that can be easily achieved through seeing and demonstration in class".

PARENTAL INVOLVEMENT

The issue of parental involvement was responded to like how the HoDs did. Teacher 6 (T6) from school F said, "About 40% of learners are doing well in reading because their parents are fully involved and supportive. Teachers become frustrated when they cannot jointly discuss the learner's challenges with parents because some learning barriers cannot be addressed when parents are not involved". Teacher 5 from school E and teacher 4 from school D with the same view said that "Some parents claimed to be unable to assist their children because they are unemployed and illiterate, and they do not have a good understanding about teaching and learning issues". Teacher 2 from school B said, "poverty and illiteracy are issues that cause children failure because most parents are from foreign African countries, they also cannot read and write Setswana. They are unemployed and cannot afford the basic needs". Teacher 1 from school A said, "It is so difficult to engage parents to assist in improving reading and writing problems because parents do not show up to school meetings. The teacher added and said: The other challenge is that some of the parents, do not understand the LoLT that is used in the Tshwane West district primary schools".

LANGUAGE BARRIER

Teacher 3 from school C said: "These learners started schooling without a background or good understanding of basic language because they are from foreign countries. As a result, learners cannot understand what is taught because of the language barrier". Hence, teacher 4 of School D and Teacher 5 from School E have acknowledged that the "language barrier is the reason why learners are unable to read and write". The evidence in this essence is, they have indicated that "it is because the learners cannot understand what they are taught in class". The concept based on the teacher's deliberation is that a good understanding of a language can play an important role for a learner to achieve. Teacher 2 of School B said, "The learner's understanding of a language could effectively improve teacher-learner interaction in class and gain productive teaching and learning".

OVERCROWDING

Teacher 2 of school B said: "About 60 to 70% of learners were admitted without proper documentation like clinic cards, birth certificates, and or parents' South African Identity documents because they are from foreign neighbouring countries; therefore, learners were placed in wrong classes and in large numbers because their age could not be justified. The other challenges were that many learners did not attend pre-schools where they are prepared for primary school, and as such, they get cramped in small venues". Teacher 4 from School D confirmed that and said: "My class consists of 50 to 60 learners and is difficult to complete the learner's attendance register in time because of a high number of learners. This consumes teaching and learning time". However, Teacher 6 from School F said, "Learner-to-teacher ratio should be 1 to 34, which the school does not adhere to and that is a reason why teachers cannot meet the desired teaching and learning set goals".

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

There is no doubt that there are major policy issues that do not assist the primary schools in the Tshwane West District to attain QE due to issues that cut across reading and writing. Even though the conceptual framework streamlined the study to reading and writing, there could be more issues that hamper the attainment of QE in the said schools. The HoDs cried foul on issues around the language barrier with the teachers too echoing the same sentiments. One of the HoDs said that the language that learners are exposed to at school is not even practiced at home. The issue of the language barrier which is seen to be the greatest challenge is echoed by Magombo (2015) who said that some children who come from areas where they speak languages other than those used in schools, find it hard to learn, either by reading and or writing through a language which is different from mother's language. This was fuelled by the lack of parental involvement who also, many of them, do not understand the language that is used in schools because they are also from neighbouring countries and or are illiterate and speak other languages other than those used in the District of Tshwane, which is Setswana. This then makes it difficult for the learners to make meaning of major concepts in the classroom because parents are not assisting in practicing reading, writing, and speaking Setswana as a basic language at home. These are some of the courses that the Department of Basic Education, DBE (2017) stated that "the underperformance of learners continued to lag". The issue of overcrowding was also raised by teachers as one of the main issues that hamper adequate instructional practices. According to Rueckert (2019), children in many countries in sub-Saharan Africa are often squeezed into overcrowded classrooms that are falling apart or are learning outside. This was found to be a common tragedy in most African countries as was also raised by Du Plessis and Mestry (2019) stating that many African countries in rural areas have serious difficulty when it comes to the provision of QE. Various factors negatively contribute to quality education, such as lack of physical resources and basic infrastructure, water, sanitation, and electricity. As a result, Ndimande (2016) said, the marginalized black children's future in township schools and educational opportunities are affected as their rights to QE are limited. An inadequate learning environment disadvantages the quality of teaching and learning at school. Learners including all people involved in the running of the school need to feel safe and comfortable in a school environment to be productive.

Textbooks were also mentioned by both the HoDs and teachers as one of the issues that make it impossible for learners to get used to doing schoolwork while they are at home because of insufficient books. This is echoed by Nasreen and Bano (2016) who said that the scarcity of textbooks and resources remains a serious challenge affecting education quality, and Rueckert (2019) encourages that textbooks, school supplies, and other tools are needed to enhance excellence. The findings of the study prove that poor reading and writing from primary school learners have dire consequences because when learners fail to excel in reading and writing at the primary school level, they most likely going to struggle with deeper concepts when they start senior primary face which would eventually affect their Further Education and Training (FET) phase. The study has found that a lack of reading and writing by the learners in the primary schools of the Tshwane West district in Pretoria is hampering the QE that should be attained. The issue of many learners coming from foreign and or neighboring countries is not an issue, but there should be a policy that binds the parents and the schools that all learners, would have gone through the pre-schools before entering primary school education for the teachers and learners to find their work cut out. Parents too, should be compelled by policy to attend parents' meetings where they are briefed on challenges that are experienced by teachers on their children. As such, the charisma of QE would be easily attained.

CONCLUSION

The study aimed to ascertain the appeal towards the attainment of quality education in primary schools in Tshwane West District, with a special focus on issues around reading and writing. Since primary education forms the foundation for secondary education, reading and writing form the backbone in that regard. Many factors came forth during the face-to-face interviews with the HoDs and the teachers. The study found that the policies that are in place in primary schools do not assist in the optimal running of the schools to attain quality education. There seem to be gaps in the existing policies that do not coerce the home or community to work hand in hand with the schools to assist learners. Classrooms are still overcrowded; learners are admitted without being screened and teachers often pick up issues of language barriers during the process of teaching and learning which end up affecting reading and writing. This is also fueled by the lack of parental involvement who are either illiterate or who do not understand the LoLT in the schools around the Tshwane West District. According to Munap and Malik (2023), a poor work environment, including factors such as excessive workload, lack of recognition and limited opportunities for growth and development can increase the risk of developing occupational stress. These outcomes of occupational stress can result in significant economic and social costs for both employers and employees. The study recommends that policies should be reviewed to accommodate all learners who are eligible to learn in South African schools and the use of LoLT needs to be prescribed to accommodate all learners who are engaged in teaching and learning. This would alleviate problems that are currently experienced in the FET phase where many learners still struggle with sentence construction, articulation of speech, and confidence during classroom activities, which, when one looks at these challenges, emanate from the primary school level.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

There is no conflict of interest in this study.

CONTRIBUTION OF AUTHOR (*optional*)

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